

IMPORTANCE OF THE PATCHWORK NEEDLEWORK IN STUDY WHICH HAS GIVEN A BIRTH TO APPLIED ARTS, BASED MUCH ON ANCIENT OLD-TIME TRADITION

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Abstract. *This article describes the history of creating one of the types of folk applied art-patchwork, which has a long history and is a vivid expression of thrift, as the use of fabric remnants not only maintains order in the house, but also new original items appear.*

Keywords: *patchwork art, patchwork skill, fragment mosaic, applique, quilt.*

Introduction

The art of patchwork has a long history. People always appreciate work and beauty. This type of art, created on the basis of manual labor, originally appeared among the poor, through pieces of fabric they quickly began to create new items necessary for the home, because in those days, beautiful and high-quality fabrics were very expensive and rare. From pieces of fabric of different colors and shapes, a decorative product is formed.

In Uzbekistan, we can refer to the works of S.Abdullayev, S.Bulatov, A.Vasikov, Prof. R.Hasanov, K.Kosimov, B. K.Kholmatov, K.M.Gulomov, M.B.Akhmedov, M.K.Mirzakhmedov, H.Egamov, M.Nabiev and many other scientists on the creative search for teaching students in art, in particular to folk applied arts.

Sources claim that samples of the art of patchwork were first found in Egyptian tombs and in China about 5,000 thousand years ago. Later, in the first middle Ages, for protection and warm walks of soldiers, coolers were created from the remains of leather and other fabrics. For example, Japanese armor is also made in the same way that it is similar to armor from the above countries. In one of the Tokyo museums, there is still an exhibition of costumes made from the remnants of fabrics belonging to about the same period. About a thousand Buddhas characteristic of the X century were found from a cave in 1920, the Buddhas were woven into a carpet made from remnants of clothing. Based on the use of this technology in the XI and XIII centuries, new manifestations of household items were discovered. Since the XVIII and XIX centuries, with the development of light industry, as a result of the numerous production of fabrics, attention to the craft of patchwork has somewhat decreased. To date, interest in such subjects is growing again. These items were now restored not only for the purpose of saving fabrics, but also at the level of art. It is worth Recalling the following opinion of the orientalist scholar Abu Nasr Farabi, who lived in the X century and devoted himself to this occupation: "One who has the superiority to discover the most beautiful and useful, and what he has discovered is really in accordance with his own desire and that of someone else, or when it is suspected that a created or created thing is really good and useful. "This idea is located in the heart of every craftsman. Of course, the artisans gathered in one place and organized one city, where the presence of large workshops, where their own rules were established, which led to bringing the products of artisans to the level of art.

Also, in the middle ages in Devon, "Nasayim ul-Muhabbat" by Alisher Navoi and in the works of the preacher Hussein Voiz Koshifiy clothing (from rags, long Uzbek robes, dervish rags)

are referred to as the clothes of saints or dervishes. Medieval representatives of mysticism are often depicted or in clothing close to it. As example, thumbnails to the product of the Kamoliddin Husayn Guzargah “Majalis ul-Ushshak”. The idea that rags or complete protects the wearer from trouble-accidents, has become popular among the people.

Study of patchwork art based on historical traditions

The word “flap” came from the word “drought”, that is, it came from the technique of weaving rags similar to the texture of a crack in the earth. From the remnants of the fabric, art masters create a new composition with a variety of mosaic patterns, using the necessary templates. In ancient times, one side, i.e. the back, consisted of flaps of calico fabric, and the front - of a composition made of pieces of fabric. Among some peoples, creating compositions using pieces of fabric is also called piece mosaic. Fragment mosaic is considered one of the directions of cross-section technique, it is also called application. Application – (lot. applicatio-gluing) processing, decorating a drawing by colorful drilling, sewing or gluing materials, other segments of various materials and papers on paper other materials. A flower made in the same way, the image is also called an application. The flap is also combined with sewing pieces of fabric on the whole background to create an image that creates a whole beauty between the original fabrics. Flaps are ornaments that are put together and assembled from small pieces; ornaments made in the same way are called flaps. From tiny pieces of fabric of different colors and shapes, a product or decoration is formed. In applied art, it is common to use; quilts, blankets, bedspreads, bed linen, tablecloths and other art objects made in the same way since ancient times.

In Russia, by the second half of the XIX century, for sale to overseas countries, decoration from the remnants of cotton fabric, later grew to the level of traditional patchwork, until the XVII century in the country, it was used mainly as a home cloth. The complete picture on the canvas was created in this way: the remnants of the fabric, from the clothes, the details were sorted and collected and stored, and ready-made clothes were created from it. It is interesting that in the middle of the XVII century, after the manufacture of sewing machines, in Russia from the remnants of fabric sewed various and simple decorative flowers on a fabric basis. In villages, mosaics are created using rectangular and triangular shiny fabric remnants. The shape of the rags is also related to the fact that the shape of the remnants of the direct forms of Russian national clothing remains rectangular, triangular and rectangular remnants.

In the XVI century, England began to create colorful, decorative fabrics made of Indian cotton. Bedding with a decorative pattern created a stylish design for the home interior. In 1712, in England, the sale of rags from Indian fabrics began to be restricted, and samples of this art began to decrease. Silk and itchy fabrics were used in the production of jagged flaps. Thick fabric calico fabric became contraband, the price of fabric in England increased at a very rapid rate. The cut-up remnants of the fabrics that were formed were not thrown out during the sewing process, other things were created from it. Fragments of various types were combined and created from the remnants of itchy and rough tissues based on the application technique. The simplest residual fabrics are sewn as one cloth on top of each other.

In the XVII century, during the awakening in the 20s in North America, samples of the art of patchwork fell into the hands of migrants. Due to a lack of materials, blankets were made from remnants of old clothing. Due to the lack of fabrics, the tradition includes quilt samples of art-bouquets created from the remnants of fabric. They over time improved their color harmony and patterns, simple American Housewives sewed quilt bouquets mainly in their homes in winter. All

American examples of applied art were created before 1750 on the basis of the flap technique. On this basis there was the traditional decoration of patchwork art. The name of many examples of art was called by words that occur in life. For example, "saw Tooth", "Bear palm", "basket for the net", etc. Later, until 1850, the art of application became widespread. Examples of art, including quilts created in the technique of patchwork art, are extremely rare. At the world exhibition of 1876, held in Philadelphia, USA, a new technical example of English art was presented – crazy (unique, famous works with the names "Spiral", "Plate", "rose"). Crazy silk fabric is made and decorated with additional floral decorations. Crazy technique uses unique fabrics-brocade, velvet, silk, which is created in any form and patterned pattern, new samples of flaps were published in 1879 in the illustrative magazine "Peterson". This direction of drawing patches is called "decorative quilt" or "Japanese silk".

Conclusion

In the process of performing the flap technique, as a result of combining pieces of fabric of different types and colors, a complete, completely different complex image is obtained. In conclusion, we can say that the flap technique has not lost its relevance at the present time, with the help of this technique, you can create unique compositions, unique outfits, household items.

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